

Twitter codebook

Academic explanatory journalism and emerging COVID-19 science

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December 6, 2022

Table of Contents

1. [Overview of Sample and Coding Protocol](#)
 2. [Coding Instructions](#)
 3. [Categories and Codes](#)
 - a. [Account Type](#)
 - b. [Actor Group](#)
 4. [References](#)
-

Overview of sample and coding protocol

Sample

Our sample consists of tweets and corresponding Twitter users sharing 40 *The Conversation* articles that feature COVID-19-related preprints that were posted to *bioRxiv* or *medRxiv* between 1 January to 30 April 2020. The final dataset contained 1828 tweets, which were shared by 1325 users.

Universe: All Twitter accounts that sent out tweets between 1 January 2020 and 6 March 2021, which mentioned or linked to an article in *The Conversation* that included a preprint about COVID-19 from one of the following venues: *bioRxiv*, *medRxiv*

Unit of analysis: Individual Twitter account.

Coding protocol

Two coders used the detailed coding instrument and coding tool (see the “Coding Instructions” and “Coding Categories”) to classify each Twitter account according to two categories: *Account Type* and *Actor Group*. Table 1 presents an overview of the three categories and their related codes.

Table 1. Category definitions and code classification.

	Twitter User Account Type	Twitter User Actor Group
References	Pew Research Center (2018); Tsou et al (2015)	Dutceac Segesten & Bossetta (2017) Gerhards & Schäfer (2010, p. 149)
Relevant codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individual ● Group ● Bot ● Unknown 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Political Actors ● Business/ Private Corporations ● Healthcare ● Civil Society organisations ● Media and Communicators ● Academia ● Citizen ● Unknown ● Other

Coding users with multiple identities

All codes were mutually exclusive. However, some Twitter User bios included descriptions that suggested they belonged to more than one Actor Group (e.g. the user was both a journalist and a medical professional, or a politician and an academic). To code these cases, the following logic was followed:

- If one of the possible Actor Groups was “Academia,” the user was coded as Academia. This coding strategy enabled us to examine the extent to which research articles and media stories about research engage audiences beyond the academic sphere.
- If the account bio included only personal information (e.g. “Mom,” or “dog lover”) the user was coded as a Citizen. However, if the account bio included information suggesting any other Actor Group (e.g. “Midwife” or “Writer”) they would be coded by that actor group, rather than as a Citizen.
- For all other cases, the identity described first in a user’s bio was coded as their dominant Actor Group (cf. Vanio & Holmberg, 2017). As Vainio and Holmberg (2017) argue, “what users describe themselves first with is the most relevant aspect for themselves.”

Use of outside sources

Following Tsou et al. (2015), coders were allowed to reference outside sources (e.g. Google, LinkedIn) in cases where a user’s Account Type or Actor Group was unclear from their Twitter bio. In such cases, coders were also encouraged to consider recent tweet activity by the user. Example sources include:

- User’s personal or professional website
- User’s linkedIn profile
- User’s Academia.edu profile

Coding Instructions

1. Use the online coding form at <https://www.cognitoforms.com/templates/shared/Scholcommlab/ConversationTweetsCodingSheet>
2. Once you are logged in, you will find an interactive spreadsheet.
 - a. Each row represents one Twitter account to be coded.
 - b. Each column contains information related to the Twitter account to be coded (those in ***bold italics*** must be filled out by the coder; all others will be automatically input into the spreadsheet):
 - ***Conversation URL***: The hyperlink to the TC story that was shared by the Twitter user
 - ***Twitter URL***: The hyperlink to the original tweet
 - ***Coder Initials***: Your initials
 - ***Duplicate***: Have you coded this Twitter user's bio before (i.e. for another tweet in the data set)?
 - ***Twitter Handle***: The Twitter user's handle (i.e. @Handle)
 - ***Twitter Name***: The Twitter user's display name at the time of data collection
 - ***Twitter Bio***: The Twitter user's bio at the time of data analysis
 - ***Account Type***: The type of account that tweeted the ***ResearchMediaURL***
 - ***Actor Group***: The actor group corresponding to the Twitter user
 - ***Notes***: User this code to note anything unusual or noteworthy about the Twitter user
3. Select the first tweet. This will open the coding entry area.
4. Code each tweet for the variables explained below, using the information provided in the coding form.
 - a. Click on the Twitter URL to view the user's profile picture and/or Twitter feed. This can provide clues about what kind of account type and actor group the user belongs to.
 - b. If the Twitter user profile provides more information, such as an outward link or an affiliation, you can also use this information for Google searches to help with the coding.
 - c. You may also research any name, organisation, or other term you are not familiar with in order to help you determine the nature of the account – but make sure you code that account based only on the information provided at the time of the tweet (use the [Web Archive](#) where needed).
 - d. If there are multiple codes within a user bio or a tweet, code for whatever is mentioned first, unless otherwise specified
5. Please use the "notes" field to document any idiosyncratic findings that may be important to the researchers (anything that is unique or stands out to you), as well as anything you are unsure about.
6. If you have any questions, please email Alice at [afleerac \[at\] sfu \[dot\] ca](mailto:afleerac@sfu.ca).

Categories and codes

Twitter Account Categories

Account Type

Brief definition: The entity the Twitter account belongs to.

Possible Values: Individual, Group, Bot, Unknown

► Individual

Select “Individual” if the Twitter account represents a single human being as distinct from a group. [singular, human]

Code users as *individual* if their profile meets 2 or more of the following criteria:

1. a human profile photo,
2. a full name (e.g. Lana Garcia),
3. a bio that uses the first person tense
4. links to a website that portrays them as an individual

If the user fulfils only 1 of these criteria, select *unknown* instead. If you are unsure for any other reason whether the Twitter account belongs to an individual, a group, or a bot, also select *unknown*.

The image shows a Twitter profile for Alice Fleerackers (@FleerackersA) with three red circles and lines pointing to specific elements that meet the criteria for being classified as an individual:

- 1** a human profile photo: Points to the circular profile picture of a woman.
- 2** a full name: Points to the name "Alice Fleerackers" and the handle "@FleerackersA".
- 3** a bio that uses the first person tense: Points to the bio text: "Writer, digital journalism & #scicomm researcher, occasional spoon carver. Find me: #scholcommlab, @SFU, @artthescience, @scienceborealis, and more. (she/her)".

Other visible profile information includes the location "Coast Salish Territory", the website "alicefleerackers.com", and the date "Joined December 2018".

▶ **Group**

Select “Group” if the Twitter account represents more than one person, including events, associations, and organisations [plural, human].

Sometimes organisations list the name of their president/representative as the user name, but the account belongs to the organisation (see below). In these cases, select “Group.”

Note: If you are unsure if the Twitter account belongs to an individual, a group, or a bot, select unknown.

▶ **Bot**

Select “Bot” if the Twitter account *self-identifies as a bot* or automated account. Note that bots can be either groups or individuals. If you select “Bot,” select Twitter Actor Group “Other.”

Note: If the Twitter account exhibits bot-like behavior but does not self-identify as a bot, do *not* code as bot. Instead, code the account based on how the user presents themselves: as an individual or group. Otherwise, select unknown.

▶ **Unknown**

Select “Unknown” if you are unsure if the Twitter account belongs to an individual (singular), a group (plural), or a bot.

Actor Group

Brief definition: Twitter Account Actor Group refers to the type of actor group the Twitter account represents.

Possible values: Academia, Healthcare, Political Actors, Media and Communications, Private Corporations, Civil Society organisations, Citizens, Other, Unknown

Notes:

- If **more than one distinct group** is fundamentally relevant in the user’s bio, code that account using the first Actor Group mentioned in the bio, unless one of the groups mentioned is **Academia** (in that case, code as Academia). Please list any secondary group in the Notes section.
- Since all individuals are also technically *Citizens*, do not use this code unless no other Actor Groups are present.
- **If the user is retired**, select **Citizen**.

► **Academia**

Brief definition: Academia is the environment or community concerned with the pursuit of research, education, and scholarship (“Academia,” n.d.). Broadly speaking, academia has the goal to advance knowledge to better understand the world we live in (as opposed to pursuing economic or policy goals).

Possible Twitter Account Types: Individual or Group

Notes: Use this code for bios that include disciplinary technical language that indicate an academic affiliation. This code does not include primary schools, high schools, or public libraries. It also excludes “former” or “lapsed” academics who are no longer affiliated with an academic institution.

Practitioners such as doctors, dietitians, or lawyers should only be categorized as “Academia” if they are affiliated with an academic or research institution. Otherwise, select “Healthcare” (for doctors and dieticians) or “Citizens” (for other practitioners). For research institutions that exist for economic or policy reasons, do not select “Academia,” but refer to one of the other groups in this codebook and leave a note if you are unsure about the coding. Research institutions affiliated with academic institutions should also be coded as “Academia,” but university press offices should not (code as “Media & Communications”).

Select “Academia” if the Twitter account belongs to **an individual member or group of:**

- Scientists or researchers based at academic/research institutions; **OR**
- Librarians based at academic/research institutions; **OR**
- Academic or research institutions; **OR**
- Scholarly societies; **OR**
- Scholarly publishers; **OR**
- Scholarly journals; **OR**
- Students in university/higher education (e.g. college, undergrad, graduate).

► Healthcare

Brief definition: The Healthcare actor group refers to **individuals or organisations** with a goal of maintaining, protecting, or recovering citizens' physical, mental, or emotional well-being, especially by trained and licensed professionals and facilities.

Possible Twitter Account Type: Individual or Group

Notes: This category includes actors working to protect or improve health at the local, regional, national, or international level. It does *not* include private corporations or unlicensed individuals promoting pharmaceutical products, "natural health" remedies, beauty/fitness routines, or other for-profit enterprises.

Select "Public Health" if the Twitter account belongs to **an individual member or group** that is employed in an official capacity to promote and protect the health of citizen, including the following:

- Public health officers; **OR**
- Hospitals, medical clinics, other public health centres; **OR**
- Professional medical associations; **OR**
- Public health organisations;
- Medical practitioners (doctors, nurses, orderlies, etc); **OR**
- Licensed alternative health practitioners (chiropractors, etc); **OR**
- Medical students

► Political Actor

Brief definition: Political actors are "those individuals who aspire, through organisational and institutional means, to influence the decision-making process. They may seek to do this by attaining institutional political power, in government or constituent assemblies, through which preferred policies can be implemented" (McNair, 2003, p. 5).

Possible Twitter Account Types: Individual or Group

Notes: This code includes actors on the local, provincial, state, federal, or international level, but *not* public health officials or organisations (see next actor group). It does not include staff working for political actors, such as personal assistants, political consultants, or communications professionals.

Select “Political actors” if the Twitter account belongs to **an individual member or group** of:

- Elected or appointed officials/offices (Executive, Legislative, Judiciary); **OR**
- Lobbyists; **OR**
- Political parties

▶ **Media and Communications**

Brief definition: Media and communications actors are organisations, individuals, outlets, or tools used to disseminate information or data. This includes print media, the news media (including online), photography, cinema, broadcasting (radio and television), advertising, and public relations. This actor group also includes meso- and macro-level social media influencers, defined, for the purposes of this study, as individual users who share “personal, authentic, credible, and down-to-earth” content with a network of more than 10,000 followers (Harrigan et al., 2021).

Possible Twitter Account Types: Individual or Group

Notes: The term “influencer” should only be applied to individual users who would otherwise be categorised as “Citizens” (i.e. Political Actors, Public Health Officials, Doctors, or Academics should be coded as such, even if they have more than 10,000 followers).

Select “Media and Communications” if the Twitter account belongs to **an individual member or group** of:

- News organisations (newspapers, magazines, TV and radio, press agencies, online news media); **OR**
- Independent journalists; **OR**
- Bloggers; **OR**
- Social media influencers; **OR**
- PR or press agencies; **OR**
- Marketing or advertising agencies

▶ **Business/Private Corporation**

Brief definition: A private corporation is a business or organisation formed by a group of people for the **purpose of generating profit**, and it has rights and liabilities separate from those of the individuals involved. This code also applies to individuals who identify as business leaders.

Possible Twitter Account Type: Group, Individual

Notes: For groups or individuals working in scholarly publishers, journals, and private corporations with an academic affiliation, see “Academia.” For media or communications organisations, see “Media and Communications.” For public healthcare, such as hospitals, health clinics, or public health offices, select “Healthcare.”

Select “Private Corporation/Business” if the Twitter account belongs to one of the following **groups**:

- Company; **OR**
- Conglomerate; **OR**
- Cooperative; **OR**
- Corporation; **OR**
- Holding company; **OR**
- Joint-stock; **OR**
- Partnership; **OR**
- General; **OR**
- Limited; **OR**
- Limited liability; **OR**
- Private limited; **OR**
- Sole proprietorship.

Select “Private Corporation/Business” if the Twitter account belongs to one of the following **individuals**:

- CEO; **OR**
- COO; **OR**
- Lead; **OR**
- Director; **OR**
- Manager; **OR**
- Head; **OR**
- Executive; **OR**
- Business Person

▶ **Civil Society Organisations**

Brief definition: Civil Society organisations are “**non-State, not-for-profit**, voluntary entities formed by people in the social sphere that are separate from the State and the market. CSOs represent a wide range of interests and ties. They can include community-based organisations as well as non-governmental organisations (NGOs). In the context of the UN Guiding Principles Reporting Framework, CSOs do not include business or for-profit associations” (Shift Project Ltd & Mazars LLP, n.d.).

Possible Twitter Account Type: Group

Notes: This excludes scholarly societies and associations, which should be coded as “Academia.” It also excludes professional journalism, media, or communications associations, which should be coded as “Media and Communications,” as well as Medical/Health-related organisations, hospitals, and clinics, which should be coded as either “Healthcare”.

Select “Civil Society Organisations” if the Twitter account belongs to one of the following **groups**:

- Activist groups; **OR**
- Charities; **OR**

- Clubs (sports, social, etc.);
OR
- Community organisations or foundations; **OR**
- Consumer organisations; **OR**
- Cooperatives; **OR**
- Foundations; **OR**
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs); **OR**
- Non-profit organisations (NPOs); **OR**
- Private voluntary organisations (PVOs); **OR**
- Professional associations;
OR
- Religious organisations; **OR**
- Social enterprises; **OR**
- Social movement organisations; **OR**
- Support groups; **OR**
- Trade unions; **OR**
- Voluntary associations.

► Citizen

Brief definition: Citizens refer to **individuals** belonging to the general public. This does not include political actors, civil society organisations, the media, academics, or any other category listed above (although, technically, all of these individuals are also citizens).

Note: Select “Citizen” if the Twitter user does not present themselves as affiliated with any of the aforementioned actor groups but appears to be an individual (e.g. has human name, a human profile picture, describes themselves as a mom, dad, brother, Christian, etc). If an account does not include any information at all in the bio, but clearly refers to an individual (i.e. because it has a human profile image and human name) code as Citizen.

Possible Twitter Account Type: Individual

► Other

Select “Other” if none of the actor groups above seem appropriate for the Twitter account. Use the “Notes” column to provide a suggested category. Also use for bots.

► Unknown

Select “Unknown” if you are unable to determine which actor group the Twitter account belongs to. Also select “Unknown” if you selected “Bot” as the account type.

References

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